

Port of Amsterdam (NL)

This fiche includes maps displaying the location of the sampling points (SPOs) around the port of Amsterdam (NL) with measurements of NO₂ and PM_{2.5} in 2023 (E1a validated data AQ e-Reporting). The tables include additional information on the annual mean concentrations of each SPO with available data (data coverage larger than 75%), distances of the SPOs from the port area, location of the SPO in one of the 8 wind sectors around the port (WS: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW), population living in the WS within 10 km from the port, and trends of annual mean concentrations (2005-2023) when available. This information has been complemented with the EEA air quality annual maps (1 km x 1 km), covering the whole area around the port and showing in the boxplot the different levels concentrations over the port area compared to the surrounding region, including the weighted area means for the different land cover classes. The presented information is based only on SPOs reported to the EEA, additional SPOs or data may exist at national level.

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Port area and NO₂ air quality SPOs around the port within 5 and 10 km

Port area and PM_{2.5} air quality SPOs around the port within 5, 10 and 20 km

Pozzoli, L., Gressent, A., Soares, J., Colette, A., Monge, S. & González Ortiz, A. (2025). Air quality around ports (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2024/12, version 2, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17416089>).
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European Environment Agency
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NO₂ SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 1)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Netherlands	NL00012	Traffic	52.39	4.89	22.45	-58.65	0.00	E	91,895
Netherlands	NL00546	Industrial	52.42	4.83	21.34		0.26	N	82,945
Netherlands	NL00019	Background	52.37	4.90	18.54	-49.48	0.28	SE	349,082
Netherlands	NL00704	Industrial	52.43	4.77	20.53	-28.62	0.28	NW	28,110
Netherlands	NL00002	Traffic	52.39	4.88	27.09	-58.61	0.32	SE	349,082
Netherlands	NL00007	Traffic	52.38	4.85	30.42	-54.66	0.61	S	219,121
Netherlands	NL00003	Background	52.39	4.94	14.58	-47.29	1.28	E	91,895
Netherlands	NL00703	Background	52.40	4.73	13.30	-49.41	1.39	W	8,773
Netherlands	NL00017	Traffic	52.36	4.90	22.15	-53.28	1.50	SE	349,082
Netherlands	NL00020	Traffic	52.37	4.86	25.34	-55.59	1.85	SE	349,082

NO₂ SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 2)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Netherlands	NL00022	Background	52.37	4.79	14.11	-40.65	2.49	SW	100,359
Netherlands	NL00014	Background	52.36	4.87	14.75	-56.94	3.06	SE	349,082
Netherlands	NL00701	Background	52.45	4.82	15.52	-46.99	3.10	N	82,945
Netherlands	NL00561	Background	52.33	4.77	18.68		6.30	SW	100,359

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PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 1)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Netherlands	NL00012	Traffic	52.39	4.89	8.71		0.00	E	91,895
Netherlands	NL00016	Background	52.39	4.87	6.78		0.00	E	91,895
Netherlands	NL00704	Industrial	52.43	4.77	8.35		0.28	NW	28,110
Netherlands	NL00007	Traffic	52.38	4.85	8.79		0.61	S	219,121
Netherlands	NL00703	Background	52.40	4.73	7.96		1.39	W	8,773
Netherlands	NL00017	Traffic	52.36	4.90	9.25		1.50	SE	349,082
Netherlands	NL00014	Background	52.36	4.87	7.71		3.06	SE	349,082
Netherlands	NL00701	Background	52.45	4.82	8.77		3.10	N	82,945
Netherlands	NL00561	Background	52.33	4.77	8.37		6.30	SW	100,359
Netherlands	NL00572	Industrial	52.47	4.63	9.12		9.24	NW	28,110

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PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 2)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Netherlands	NL00570	Background	52.49	4.64	8.14		9.74	NW	28,110
Netherlands	NL00551	Industrial	52.46	4.60	8.14		10.19	NW	28,110
Netherlands	NL49557	Industrial	52.49	4.60	9.90		11.87	NW	28,110
Netherlands	NL00553	Industrial	52.49	4.60	8.58		12.01	NW	28,110
Netherlands	NL00573	Industrial	52.48	4.58	9.68		12.35	NW	28,110
Netherlands	NL00556	Background	52.56	4.86	6.58		14.69	N	82,945

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Annual mean NO₂ concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the port area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

- High density residential
- Low density residential
- Industry
- Traffic
- Agricultural areas
- Natural areas

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Annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2023

EEA air quality map (1 km x 1 km)

Concentrations over the port area compared to the surrounding region. Coloured dots correspond to weighted area means for different land cover classes in the surrounding region.

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